

Fig. (2) The overflow of YOLO. It starts by dividing the input into grid, followed by bounding boxes confidence prediction and class probabilities of each grid cell, which are multiplied to generate the final detection result.

frames. We resized 250 frames, ignoring temperatures less than 16.

We identified three object classes, human, ignore and static, and annotated3 the boxes in these 250 images using the Labelme[4] tool.

Fig. (3) Thermal image labelling.

Annotation time we used YOLO original format i.e. image and annotated txt file was including:

Object Class + X-center + Y-center + Width + Height
where:

- Object Class - integer object number from 0 to (classes-1)
- X-center, Y-center, Width, Height - float values relative to width and height of image, it can be equal from (0.0 to 1.0)

B. Network Architecture

YOLO use a backed of conv2D, leaky relu and max pooling for pattern detection, then a prediction layer composed of two densely connected layers. The first one large and the second one smaller that returns the predictions for each of cells.

Our data is too simple for the full tiny-YOLO architecture, so we created a simpler model4, similar to YOLO with fewer layers, that was good enough and train faster.

conv2d (Conv2D)	(None, 64, 64, 8)	16
leaky_re_lu (LeakyReLU)	(None, 64, 64, 8)	0
max_pooling2d (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 32, 32, 8)	0
conv2d_1 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 32, 16)	144
conv2d_2 (Conv2D)	(None, 32, 32, 32)	544
leaky_re_lu_1 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 32, 32, 32)	0
max_pooling2d_1 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 16, 16, 32)	0
conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 16, 32)	1056
conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(None, 16, 16, 64)	2112
leaky_re_lu_2 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 16, 16, 64)	0
max_pooling2d_2 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 8, 8, 64)	0
conv2d_5 (Conv2D)	(None, 8, 8, 64)	4160
conv2d_6 (Conv2D)	(None, 8, 8, 128)	8320
leaky_re_lu_3 (LeakyReLU)	(None, 8, 8, 128)	0
max_pooling2d_3 (MaxPooling2D)	(None, 4, 4, 128)	0
conv2d_7 (Conv2D)	(None, 2, 2, 64)	73792
conv2d_8 (Conv2D)	(None, 2, 2, 32)	2080
flatten (Flatten)	(None, 128)	0
dense (Dense)	(None, 128)	16512
reshape_7 (Reshape)	(None, 4, 4, 8)	0
Total params: 108,736		
Trainable params: 108.736		

Fig. (4) Our model architecture

As can be seen from the last Reshape layer of the model4, we chose to use a 4x4 grid as we are dealing with small photos instead of the 7x7 grid used in the original model. We set it to make only one box prediction with its confidence value for each grid. At the end of this, we set the output layer we modified to be 4x4x8, which is:

$C = 3$, which are human, static, ignore
 $B = 1$

$$4 \times 4 \times 8 = 4 \times 4 \times (C + B \times 5) \quad (2)$$

1) *Strategies of Layers Combinations:* Beyond individual layers, YOLO use three main techniques to capture informations inside images : Multiple stacked conv2D, max pooling and conv2D with 1x1 kernels. Those are respectively used by YOLO in order to split images in features, reduce image and select best channels. We didn't found a good explanation of why this specific architecture is the best. The reasons described after for picking each type of layer below are our best guess for YOLO.

Multiple stacked Conv2D purpose is to improve the range of captation of information without increasing the computation too much. As an example, two stacked Conv2D with 3x3 kernels have a range of 5 pixels around the current pixel. We could use a 5x5 kernel for the same capture range, but that would require more computation for the convolution layer. Remember that channels actually are 3x3xnb output channels.

Max Pooling has a similar purpose as stacked Conv2D with a very different process. It reduces channels by picking only the most activated values at some point. This helps in reducing the noise and also improve the computation as the channels size are reduced by 4.

Conv2D with 1x1 kernel have a very different purpose than Conv2D with larger kernel, so I take it apart. It acts as a filter that select the best features in a channels set and group them as a new channels set. I had difficulties understanding 1x1 filter at the beginning because I was thinking that Conv2D was using a 2D kernel. It's not : the kernel is 3D with a third dimension equal to the number of channels. The reason is that when you stack convolution one after the other, the next layer actually has an input that is not one image but a stack of images (also called filters). Conv2D operate in 2 dimension but process a 3 dimension input. Once you know that it's clear how 1x1 convolution is useful in picking informations inside filter and combining them into a smaller number of layers.

2) *Custom Loss Function*: Normally, when we look at the first loss function defined in Yolo's first article, we see the following features:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \lambda_{\text{coord}} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{\text{obj}} \left[(x_i - \hat{x}_i)^2 + (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2 \right] \rightarrow \text{Bounding Box Location (x, y) when there is object} \\
 & + \lambda_{\text{coord}} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{\text{obj}} \left[\left(\frac{w_i - \hat{w}_i}{w_i} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{h_i - \hat{h}_i}{h_i} \right)^2 \right] \rightarrow \text{Bounding Box size (w, h) when there is object} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{\text{obj}} (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2 \rightarrow \text{Confidence when there is object} \\
 & + \lambda_{\text{noobj}} \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \sum_{j=0}^B \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{\text{noobj}} (C_i - \hat{C}_i)^2 \rightarrow \text{Confidence when there is no object} \\
 & + \sum_{i=0}^{S^2} \mathbb{1}_{ij}^{\text{obj}} \sum_{c \in \text{classes}} (p_i(c) - \hat{p}_i(c))^2 \rightarrow \text{Class probabilities when there is object}
 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. (5) First introduced YOLO model loss function detailed explanation

- 1st term (x, y): The bounding box x and y coordinates is parametrized to be offsets of a particular grid cell location so they are also bounded between 0 and 1. And the sum of square error (SSE) is estimated only when there is object.
- 2nd term (w, h): The bounding box width and height are normalized by the image width and height so that they fall between 0 and 1. SSE is estimated only when there is object. Since small deviations in large boxes matter less than in small boxes. square root of the bounding box

width w and height h instead of the width and height directly to partially address this problem.

- 3rd term and 4th term (The confidence) (i.e. the IOU between the predicted box and any ground truth box): In every image many grid cells do not contain any object. This pushes the “confidence” scores of those cells towards zero, often overpowering the gradient from cells that do contain objects, and makes the model unstable. Thus, the loss from confidence predictions for boxes that don't contain objects, is decreased, i.e. $\lambda_{\text{noobj}}=0.5$.
- 5th term (Class Probabilities): SSE of class probabilities when there is objects.
- coord: Due to the same reason mentioned in 3rd and 4th terms, coord = 5 to increase the loss from bounding box coordinate predictions.

We used the same one-to-one loss function in our project, with the only difference being grid S=4 and number of predicted bounding box per grid B=1

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND TRAINING DETAILS

We implemented our model using the keras-tensorflow framework. While creating our model, we considered the amount of ram our device has, 192kb, so the total number of processes in each layer cannot be more than 50000.

After creating a total of 4 block conv-maxpool layers, on top of it we have added two convolutional and dense layer with size 128 then we have used Reshape layer(4x4x8) from Keras for easy computation of the custom loss function.

Then we wrote our function that should read the data and encode the labels. This function works as follows, first, it was created by determining the grid where the center of the object is located, calculating the rate of the point where that center falls on the grid, and writing it to the relevant channel.

Then we implemented the necessary function to calculate the intersection over union loss and the Custom loss function as written in the original article. Details can be better understood from the code we have written.

We separated 10 of the 250 thermal images that we had annotated for testing and trained the remaining 240 on 30 epochs. You can see the change in the loss function7 from the picture.

Then we implemented the Non Maximum Suppression algorithm to use prediction time. Normally, our model can make 16 different box predictions, as can be seen from the structure, but we need to choose the one that best covers the object. The purpose of non-max suppression is to select the best bounding box for an object and reject or “suppress” all other bounding boxes. The NMS takes two things into account:

Fig. (6) Predictions example

- 1) The objectiveness score is given by the model
- 2) The overlap or IOU of the bounding boxes

You can see the image below6, along with the bounding boxes, the model returns an objectiveness score. This score denotes how certain the model is, that the desired object is present in this bounding box. The non-max suppression will first select the bounding box with the highest objectiveness score. And then remove all the other boxes with high overlap.

Normally, Mean Average Precision needs to be calculated to evaluate how well object detection models are working. However, we did not implement this part because we do not have enough annotated data. You can see some prediction results of our model from the picture8.

Fig. (7) Change in loss during training

After training and preparing our model, we cut the reshape layer using the model.pop() function in Keras to use it on the STM32 device. Because CubeMX does not support this layer. Then we saved our model in tf.lite format. In other words, the model that we will insert into the STM32 device will actually make a 128 array prediction for us. After this point, we have implemented the necessary mathematics in the C code to make the predictions in a right way.

V. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

We noticed that our model usually detects human objects with a high confidence level, which is due to

Fig. (8) Some examples from model predictions

id	layer (type)	output shape	param #	connected to	maac	com
0	servicing_default_conv2d_9_input0 (Input)	(64, 64, 3)				
1	conv2d_9 (Conv2D)	(64, 64, 8)	32	servicing_default_conv2d_9_229,384	128	
2	pool_2 (Pool)	(32, 32, 8)		ml_1		
3	conv2d_3 (Conv2D)	(32, 32, 16)	144	pool_2	131,088	576
4	conv2d_4 (Conv2D)	(32, 32, 32)	544	conv2d_3	655,392	2,176
5	ml_3 (NonLinearity)	(32, 32, 32)		conv2d_4		
6	pool_6 (Pool)	(16, 16, 32)		ml_5		
7	conv2d_7 (Conv2D)	(16, 16, 32)	1,056	pool_6	262,176	4,224
8	conv2d_8 (Conv2D)	(16, 16, 64)	2,112	conv2d_7	589,888	8,448
9	ml_9 (NonLinearity)	(16, 16, 64)		conv2d_8		
10	pool_10 (Pool)	(8, 8, 64)		ml_9		
11	conv2d_11 (Conv2D)	(8, 8, 64)	4,160	pool_10	262,208	16,640
12	conv2d_12 (Conv2D)	(8, 8, 128)	8,320	conv2d_11	557,184	33,280
13	ml_13 (NonLinearity)	(8, 8, 128)		conv2d_12		
14	pool_14 (Pool)	(4, 4, 128)		ml_13		
15	conv2d_15 (Conv2D)	(2, 2, 64)	73,792	pool_14	294,976	295,168
16	conv2d_16 (Conv2D)	(2, 2, 32)	2,080	conv2d_15	8,224	8,320
17	reshape_17 (Reshape)	(128,)		conv2d_16		
18	dense_18 (Dense)	(128,)	16,512	reshape_17	16,384	66,048

(a) Model Architecture

id	layer (type)	maac	com
0	conv2d_0 (Conv2D)		7.6%
2	conv2d_2 (Conv2D)		4.4%
4	conv2d_4 (Conv2D)		21.8%
7	conv2d_7 (Conv2D)		8.7%
8	conv2d_8 (Conv2D)		19.6%
11	conv2d_11 (Conv2D)		6.7%
12	conv2d_12 (Conv2D)		18.5%
15	conv2d_15 (Conv2D)		9.3%
16	conv2d_16 (Conv2D)		0.3%
18	dense_18 (Dense)		0.5%

(b) Graph Analysis

the fact that there are too many annotated human objects when we examine the dataset distribution. While deploying our model inside the STM32F42910, we canceled the Non-maximum suppression part. Because our model can predict a maximum of 16 boxes in total, so for computational efficiency, we only drew boxes with a confidence level above 0.6. Our model works in under 1 second inside the microcontroller.

VI. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, we have shown how an object detection model can be developed depending on the desired conditions in cases where some ready-to-use production ready object detection models are not sufficient. The model we

(a) Image

(b) Detected boxes

(c) Image

(d) Detected boxes

(e) Image

(f) Detected boxes

Fig. (10) Some examples from STM32F429

- [2] J. Redmon and A. Farhadi, "Yolov3: An incremental improvement," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1804.02767, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1804.02767>
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- [4] K. Wada, "Labelme: Image Polygonal Annotation with Python." [Online]. Available: <https://github.com/wkentaro/labelme>

have produced can be trained with much more annotated data and improved with fine-tuning and hyper-tuning. In addition, the success of the model can be better measured by calculating the mean Average Precision on the test set. However, in general, this study shows the pipeline of how the object detection model can be created by considering the restrictions inside a microcontroller. There is actually a lot of room for improvement here, which will be a source of light and hope for future studies.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Redmon, S. K. Divvala, R. B. Girshick, and A. Farhadi, "You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection," *CoRR*, vol. abs/1506.02640, 2015. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1506.02640>